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A 1-m scale instrumented axial flow tidal turbine test bed for UNH Wave and Towing Tank

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Abstract

Under the Atlantic Marine Energy Center (AMEC) work scope, UNH and XFlow Energy jointly designed a 1-m scale axial flow turbine (AFT) test bed to evaluate different rotor configurations under various flow conditions and add testing infrastructure to the UNH Wave and Towing Tank. The combination of the 1-m scale and achievable towing speeds allows for testing in a regime where turbine performance becomes independent of Reynolds number. The primary function of the AFT test bed is to facilitate experiments that test and improve AFT designs and to provide data for model validation and verification (V&V) to the nascent marine energy industry. Examples of research applications include testing different blade designs and materials, quantifying the effects of turbulence, yaw, and upstream obstacles on turbine performance and loading, determining wake characteristics downstream of the device, and conducting scale tests of reference model turbines. The new test bed also enables UNH to elevate their testing capabilities to better align with marine energy standards published by the International Electrotechnical Commission (IEC), specifically IEC TS 62600-202. Lessons learned from testing campaigns can be used to provide feedback to the IEC to help further develop their standards.

Keywords: axial flow turbine; current energy conversion; machine design; laboratory experimental testing

1. Introduction & Background

Marine energy, including tidal, riverine and ocean currents, is a significant renewable energy resource that can be harnessed by various technologies, including axial-flow and cross-flow hydrokinetic turbines. The University of New Hampshire (UNH), as part of the Atlantic Marine Energy Center, conducts laboratory research relating to current energy converters at the Jere E. Chase Ocean Engineering Laboratory. The Wave and Towing Tank at the Chase Lab is currently configured to install and test cross-flow hydrokinetic turbines and has produced significant research relating to these devices [1, 2]. However, it is currently not configured to efficiently support the testing of axial-flow hydrokinetic turbines. To fill this infrastructure gap, UNH and XFlow Energy jointly designed a 1-m scale AFT test bed to evaluate different rotor configurations under various flow conditions. The AFT test bed was designed for testing in accordance with IEC TS 62600-202 [3] and can accommodate turbines that are at Stage 2, or Technology Readiness Level (TRL) of 4.

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The test bed supports rotors up to 1 meter in diameter, which maintains a reasonable blockage ratio between the rotor and tank cross-sectional area of 8.8%, as well as enables turbine performance independent of chord based Reynolds number (Re_c) for certain ranges of tip speed ratios and tow speeds. Chord based Reynolds number is defined as

$$Re_c \equiv \frac{\rho U_{rel} c}{\mu} \quad (1)$$

where ρ is fluid density, U_{rel} is the relative velocity experienced by the turbine blade, c is the blade chord length, and μ is dynamic viscosity. The relative velocity for a given radial location on the turbine blade of an AFT and neglecting induction is given as

$$U_{rel} = U_{\infty} \sqrt{1 + \lambda^2 \left(\frac{r}{R}\right)^2} \quad (2)$$

where U_{∞} is the carriage tow speed, λ (TSR) is the ratio between the tangential speed of the blade tip and the inflow velocity, r is the local radius from the turbine rotor axis, and R is the rotor radius [3]. While this range is determined experimentally, previous research and standards provided target ranges that helped inform the design of the test bed. IEC TS 62600-20, a Technical Specification for best practices for early stage testing of tidal energy converters, recommends that Stage 2 / TRL 4 tests are performed at a chord based Reynolds number within or above a critical value range of 200,000 to 500,000 at 70% of the turbine rotor radius [3]. Fontaine et al. found that the performance results of their 1:8.7-scale reference hydrokinetic turbine became independent of Re_c at values above $\sim 350,000$ [4]. This value was an important consideration for the AFT test bed, as the initial 1-m scale turbine selected for testing will use the same family of hydrofoil sections, MHKF1, as the Fontaine et al. study for the turbine blades. Fig. 1 below illustrates the relationship between chord-based Reynolds number and tip speed ratio for various tow speeds at 70% span. As seen below, the AFT test bed will be able to achieve the critical chord-based Reynolds numbers where performance will become independent of Reynolds number.

Fig. 1. Chord based Reynolds number vs. tip speed ratio (TSR) for tow speeds ranging from 1 to 2 m/s.

Nomenclature

AD	Analog to Digital
AFT	Axial Flow Turbine
DAQ	Data Acquisition
IEC	International Electrotechnical Commission
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
TSR	Tip Speed Ratio
c	chord length
r	local radius from turbine rotor axis
R	rotor radius
Re_c	chord based Reynolds number
U_∞	carriage/tow speed
λ	tip speed ratio
μ	fluid dynamic viscosity
ρ	fluid density

2. Technical Description & Methods

The new UNH-AMEC AFT test bed allows testing of various blades attached to the existing hub, or the testing of complete stand-alone rotors attached to the test bed shaft. The system features a sealed nacelle with a geared servo-generator drivetrain and a performance measurement system that is submersible to depths of eight feet. The rotor hub and one singular blade are equipped with multi-axis load cells to measure applied torque and thrust and flapwise and edgewise blade root bending moments, respectively. Both load cells will integrate into the existing Wave and Towing Tank's data acquisition (DAQ) and control system. A model of the turbine is shown below in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. AFT test bed assembly including key components: 1) rotor nose cone, 2) blade root bending moment transducer, 3) blade, 4) rotor hub torque & thrust transducer, 5) transducer amplifier & AD converter, 6) shaft coupling, 7) gearbox, 8) servomotor, 9) water pump assembly, 10) support structure mast (truncated), and 11) nacelle.

3. Test Bed Commissioning & Initial Experiments

Prior to investigating research questions, initial tow tests must be completed to characterize the typical performance of the turbine. It is important at this stage in commissioning to determine at what tow speeds and tip speed ratios turbine performance becomes independent of chord based Reynolds number effects. This tow speed range is found empirically by selecting various target rotor and carriage speeds and evaluating performance data over an integer number of rotations during steady state operation. This speed, or one slightly above, will become the minimum tow speed at which experiments will be conducted. Following this initial test bed and turbine characterization, research questions relating to operation under yawed conditions or turbulent inflow can be addressed.

The MHKF1 series of hydrofoils were selected as the first set of blades to be tested as they are specifically made for marine hydrokinetic rotors [5]. Additionally, previous experiments conducted at Pennsylvania State University's Applied Research Laboratory used the same blade profile and will serve as a basis for comparison of future testing [4]. Data outputs for the test bed include power vs. tow speed or non-dimensional power coefficient (C_p) vs. TSR, thrust vs. tow speed or non-dimensional thrust coefficient (C_T) vs. TSR, torque vs. tow speed or non-dimensional torque coefficient (C_Q) vs. TSR, and flapwise and edgewise blade root bending moment data. Test bed maintenance and operation positions are shown below in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3. (a) AFT test bed retracted onto carriage for maintenance; (b) turbine returned to operating position; (c) front-facing view of turbine in tank during testing.

4. Summary

A 1-m AFT test bed for the UNH Wave and Towing Tank was designed and built, which will allow direct measurements of turbine torque and thrust and blade root bending moments. The scale of the test bed allows turbine to operate at blade chord Reynolds numbers where turbine performance becomes independent of Reynolds number. Additionally, the system was designed to allow testing according to TS 62600-202 Stage 2 (TRL 4) and is expected to be useful in evaluating marine turbine designs at that Stage and TRL and contribute towards fundamental research questions.

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